

Investigation of Fomo Levels of Young Athletes in Terms of Different Variables

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ABSTRACT

The aim of this study is to examine the FOMO (Fear of Missing Out) levels of young athletes in terms of different variables. The study group of the research consisted of a total of 200 young athletes, 66 of whom were female and 134 of whom were male. The FOMO Scale developed by Przybylski et al. (2013) and adapted into Turkish by Gökler et al. (2016) was used as a data collection tool. In the analysis of the data obtained, parametric tests were used since the data showed normal distribution. One-way variant analysis was used to compare the averages of more than two variables, and Independent sample T-Test was used to compare the averages between two different variables. The data were analysed with SPSS 25.0 package programme. According to the findings of the study, FOMO levels of young female athletes were higher than young male athletes. In addition, the FOMO levels of young athletes playing individual sports were higher than those playing team sports. However, no significant difference was found between the FOMO levels of athletes according to other variables such as club league status, licence status and years of playing licensed sports. Among the age groups, FOMO levels of young athletes in the 16-17 age group were found to be higher than the other age groups. Similarly, in the variable of frequency of training participation, the FOMO levels of young athletes who participated in half of the training sessions were found to be higher than the others. These results suggest that FOMO levels of young athletes may vary depending on different variables.

Keywords: FOMO, Fear of Missing Out, Young Athletes.

Genç Sporcuların Fomo Düzeylerinin Farklı Değişkenler Açısından İncelenmesi

ÖZET

Bu çalışmanın amacı, genç sporcuların FOMO (Gelişmeleri Kaçırma Korkusu) düzeylerini farklı değişkenler açısından incelenmesidir. Araştırmanın çalışma grubunu 66'sı kadın, 134'ü erkek olmak üzere toplamda 200 genç sporcu oluşturmuştur. Veri toplama aracı olarak Przybylski ve diğerleri (2013) tarafından geliştirilen ve Gökler ve ark, (2016) tarafından Türkçe 'ye uyarlanan FOMO Ölçeği kullanılmıştır. Elde edilen verilerin analizinde veriler normal dağılım gösterdiği için parametrik testler kullanılmıştır. İki'den fazla değişkenin ortalamaları karşılaştırılırken Tek yönlü varyant analizi, iki farklı değişken arasındaki ortalamaları karşılaştırmak için ise Bağımsız örneklem T-Testi kullanılmıştır. Verilerin analizi SPSS 25.0 paket program ile yapılmıştır. Araştırmanın bulgularına göre, genç kadın sporcuların FOMO düzeyleri genç erkek sporculardan daha yüksek çıkmıştır. Ayrıca, bireysel spor yapan genç sporcuların FOMO düzeyleri takım sporları yapanlardan daha yüksektir. Ancak, sporcuların kulüp lig statüsü, lisans statüsü ve lisanslı spor yapma yılları gibi diğer değişkenlere göre FOMO düzeyleri arasında anlamlı bir farka rastlanmamıştır. Yaş grupları arasında ise 16-17 yaş grubundaki genç sporcuların FOMO düzeyleri diğer yaş gruplarından daha yüksek bulunmuştur. Benzer şekilde, antrenmana katılım sıklığı değişkeninde ise; antrenmanların yarısına katılan genç sporcuların FOMO düzeyleri diğerlerinden daha yüksek bulunmuştur. Bu sonuçlar, genç sporcuların FOMO düzeylerinin farklı değişkenlere bağlı olarak değişebileceğini göstermektedir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: FOMO, Kaybetme Korkusu, Genç Sporcular.

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Introduction

Today, individuals' relations and social interactions with others gain importance by moving to different platforms. Especially the ease of access to the internet and the interest of social networks in this environment have made it easier for people to be informed about each other. This has created the need for people to be constantly informed about the lives outside themselves. The concept of FOMO, which covers the excessive or extreme experience of this need, emerges. The concept of FOMO is defined as a widespread concern that others may be experiencing rewarding experiences even though the person is not (Przybylski, Murayama, & DeHaan, 2013). People with this concern are characterised by a desire to constantly stay in touch with what others are doing. People who have a fear of missing something often turn to social media (Przybylski, Murayama, & DeHaan, 2013).

Increasing use of social media has transformative effects on individuals' work life and lives. Increased information sharing and more social media addiction make individuals worry that they always miss some information and mobile users' sense of missing out on developments emerges. FOMO has particularly affected the interpersonal relationships and behaviours of social media users (Wang et al. 2021). The individual using social media increases the need to get information about how peers live their lives and what they do in their lives and makes them increasingly prone to fear of missing out (Eskiler, Örgen, 2022).

When the studies conducted within the scope of this subject are examined, Yıldırım and Kışioğlu (2018) stated in their study that technological developments have negative aspects as well as positive aspects and that this negativity is the increase in communication through social media instead of face-to-face interaction of individuals and that this situation negatively affects our cultural characteristics or the individual's work life, families, friends, in short, it is concluded that negativities such as not allocating enough time to the social environment are experienced.

Especially on young people, it was concluded that this situation negatively affects their academic success (Yıldırım, Kışioğlu, 2018). In addition, it was concluded that there is no significant relationship between FOMO and happiness and that female students have high FOMO behaviour in gender variable and FOMO behaviours (Kartol, Peker, 2020).

In another study, the relationship between life satisfaction and FOMO was examined and it was found that individuals with high life satisfaction had low FOMO levels (Jood, 2017). In addition, it was stated that FOMO plays a mediating role in reducing the academic achievement and motivation levels of university students (Alt, 2015). In the study conducted by Zıvdr and Karakul (2023), it was revealed that the relationship between university students' social media addiction levels and FOMO (fear of missing developments) was positive. The study also found that students with social media addiction had high levels of FOMO. It was stated that FOMO affects the control abilities of individuals such as addictive substances. In addition, it was concluded that there is an opposite relationship between healthy eating and social media addiction (Çoşkun & Demir, 2021).

Considering the above information and studies, high FOMO level affects individuals negatively. Another area where this negative effect can be seen is the field of sports and athletes. Sports are activities that contribute positively to the psychological, social and cultural development of the individual by performing movements that allow the physical and cognitive skills of the individual to work in coordination, with or without competition within the framework of predetermined rules (Tunç, 2000; cited in Günel, 2022). It is a known fact that sports activities carried out within the framework of a certain programme and plan have positive effects on young people (Özdoğru, 2018). Therefore, the participation of young people in sports should be encouraged and it becomes important to determine the factors that will prevent this. FOMO is a feature that has the possibility of distancing young athletes from these areas. When the sports sciences literature is examined,

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there are few studies with the concept of FOMO. Ceyhan and Cakır (2021) examined the FOMO levels of students studying at the physical education and sports college in terms of different variables. According to the results of the research, the FOMO levels of university students differed according to the department they studied and the duration of social media use. In the study of Saraç et al. (2023), the relationship between fear of missing developments and motivation and achievement goals was examined. As a result of the study, FOMO was found to be related to both variables.

In addition, athletes with high levels of FOMO are motivated to be evaluated positively by other athletes and to receive positive feedback (performance approach), to make an effort not to look bad to other people (performance avoidance), and to make an effort not to fall below their past performance (mastery avoidance).

People with high FOMO level neglect their work life and education life. While FOMO was previously the fear of missing developments in face-to-face environments, today, with the widespread use of social media and the internet, this fear has been transferred to digital or social media environments. Now people spend more time on social media rather than face-to-face environments. For this reason, young people are likely to stay away from sports environments due to the effects of sports participation. Since there are no similar studies conducted with young athletes in the literature, it is important to determine the FOMO levels of young athletes and the variables affecting the FOMO level. For this reason, the aim of this study is to determine the FOMO levels of young athletes and to analyse them in terms of different variables. For this purpose, the following problem statement and sub-problem statements were tried to be answered.

Problem Statement

Do FOMO levels of young athletes differ in terms of different variables?

Sub Problems

- 1) Do the FOMO levels of young athletes differ according to individual or team sports variables?
- 2) Is there a difference in FOMO levels of young athletes according to gender variable?
- 3) Do FOMO levels of young athletes differ according to the year of sportsmanship variable?
- 4) Do the FOMO levels of young athletes differ according to the amateur or professional variable of the athlete?
- 5) Do the FOMO levels of young athletes differ according to the athlete's branch variable?
- 6) Do FOMO levels of young athletes differ according to the age variable of the athlete?
- 7) Do the FOMO levels of young athletes differ according to the frequency of the athlete's weekly training participation or frequency of training?

Method

Methodological Model of the Research

In this study, survey design, one of the quantitative research methods, was used. The survey model is "studies that aim to collect data to determine certain characteristics of a group" (Büyüköztürk et al., 2020, p.16). In the current study, since the FOMO characteristics of young athletes will be determined, the mentioned screening model was preferred. 'Burdur Mehmet Akif Ersoy University Research Project Evaluation Report' permission (meeting date: 05.07.2023, meeting no: 2023/07, decision no: GO 2023/395) was obtained for the research.

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The study group of the research consists of 200 young athletes aged between 12 and 21 in Burdur province. Power analysis was performed to determine the sample size of the study and to increase the power to represent the population. Power analysis is used to determine the minimum number of samples needed for different types of analyses (Cohen, 1992). When the effect size ($|\rho|=0.5$), $\alpha=0.05$ and power ($1-\beta$) were taken as 0.95 in the power analysis performed for T-test with G*Power 3.1 package programme (Keskin, 2020). The number of samples to be studied was found to be at least 176. In order to support and make the Power Analyses reliable, the sample of the study consists of a total of 200 young athletes, 66 female and 136 male, selected by simple probability (random) sampling method. Simple probability sampling method is used to increase the power of the sample to represent the universe and to give equal chances to each unit in the universe (Ekiz, 2020, p.114).

Data Collection Tools

The FOMO (Fear of Missing Out) Scale, developed by Przybylski, et al. (2013) and adapted to Turkish culture by Gökler et al. (2016), was used as a data collection tool in the study. This scale is a measurement tool that helps to determine the FOMO level of individuals. The scale is 5-point Likert type and consists of 10 items and one dimension. In the adaptation phase of the scale, Cronbach's Alpha test reliability coefficient was found to be .81. As a result of the reliability analysis conducted for the current study, it was found to be .80. Looking at the literature, it is seen that this value is among the highly reliable values (Can, 2020, p.393).

Analysing the Data

Before analysing the obtained data, it was tested whether the data showed a normal distribution. Skewness and Kurtosis normality coefficient values were examined to determine the normal distribution of the data. When these values are between -1.96 and +1.96, it is accepted that the

data are close to normal distribution (Can, 2014; p.85). According to the normality results in Table 2, it is seen that the values are between these values specified in the literature. For this reason, parametric tests were used in the study. One-way variant analysis was used to compare the means of more than two variables, and independent sample T-Test was used to compare the means between two different variables. SPSS 25.0 package programme was used for data analysis.

Findings

Table 1. Frequency Analyses of Demographic Characteristics of the Study Group

Variable	Sub Variable	N	%
Gender	Male	134	67,0
	Girl	66	33,0
Your branch	Team Sports	146	73,0
	Individual Sports	54	27,0
Sport Club League Status	Amateur League	172	86,0
	Professional League	28	14,0
Licence Status	Amateur Licence	176	88,0
	Professional Licence	24	12,0
Age	12-13 years old	45	22,5
	14-15 years old	23	11,5
	16-17 years old	25	12,5
	18-19 years old	61	30,5
	20-21 years old	46	23,0
Weekly Training Participation or Frequency of Training	I attend all training sessions	121	60,5
	I attend at most one training session	41	20,5
	I attend half of the training	15	7,5
	I'll join you for training from time to time.	23	11,5
How Many Years Licensed Athlete	1-2 Years	79	39,5
	3-4 Years	40	20,0
	5-6 Years	47	23,5
	7 Years and above	34	17,0

Table 1 When analysed, a total of 200 young athletes, 66 (33.0%) females and 134 (67.0%) males, participated in the study. The majority of the participants (30.5%) were in the 18-19 age range consisting of 61 participants, while the 20-21 age range consisted of 46 participants (23.0%), the 12-13 age range consisted of 45 participants (22.5%), the 16-17 age range consisted of 25 participants (12.5%), and the 14-15 age range consisted of 23 participants (11.5%). When the branch status of the participants is analysed, it is seen that 146 people (73.0%) are in team sports and 54 people (27.0%) are in individual sports.

When the licence status of young athletes is examined, it is seen that 176 (88,0%) of them have amateur licence and 24 (12,0%) of them have professional licence. When the club status of the young athletes is analysed, it is seen that 172 (86,0%) of them are competing in amateur league and 28 (14,0%) of them are competing in professional league. When the frequency of training participation or frequency of training per week of young athletes is examined, it is seen that there are 121 people (60,5%) who participate in all training, 41 people (20,5%) who participate in at most one training, 15 people (7,5%) who participate in half of the training, 23 people (11,5%) who participate in training occasionally. In addition, when it is examined how many years the young athletes have been licensed athletes, it is seen that 1-2 years 76 people (39,5%), 3-4 years 40 people (20,0%), 5-6 years 47 people (23,5%), 7 years and over 34 people (17,0%).

Table 2. Arithmetic Mean, Standard Deviation Values and Normality Analysis Results of FOMO (Fear of Missing Developments) Scale.

	N	Average	Ss.	Skewness	kurtosis
Total Points	200	26,41	7,87	0,49	0,01

When the findings in Table 2 are analysed, it is seen that the total mean score of FOMO levels of young athletes is 26,41. According to this result, it can be said that the young athletes participating in the research have a moderate level of FOMO (fear of missing out on developments). In addition, skewness and kurtosis tests were applied to test whether the scale used in the research showed normal distribution. As a result of the test, the values were found to be in the range of -1.5 and +1.5 and parametric tests were used in the analysis of the data (Can, 2014).

Table 3. T Test Results Related to Fomo Levels of Young Athletes According to Their Gender

Size	Gender	N	Average	Ss.	df	t	p
Fomo Level	Male	134	25,23	7,01	198	-3,06	0,00
	Woman	66	28,78	8,97			

p<0.05

When the findings in Table 3 are analysed, it is seen that the FOMO level scores of young athletes (t=3,061, p<0.05) differ significantly according to gender variable. Accordingly, FOMO levels of female athletes (mean=28,78) are higher than FOMO levels of male athletes (mean=25,23).

Table 4. T Test Results Regarding FOMO Levels of Young Athletes According to Their Branches

Size	Branch	N	Average	Ss.	df	t	p
Fomo Variables	Team Sports	146	25,73	7,51	198	-2,01	0,04
	Individual Sports	54	28,24	8,57			

p<0.05

When the findings in Table 4 are analysed, FOMO level scores of young athletes (t=-2,016, p<0.05) differ significantly according to the branch variable. Accordingly, the FOMO levels of young athletes in individual sports (mean=28,24) are higher than the FOMO levels of young athletes in team sports (mean=25,73).

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Table 5. T Test Results Regarding FOMO Levels of Youth Athletes According to the League Status of Their Clubs

Size	SYKLS	N	Average	Ss.	df	t	p
Fomo Variables	Amateur League	17	26,71	7,70	198	1,36	0,17
	Professional League	28	24,53	8,71			

$p > 0.05$

When the findings in Table 5 are analysed, FOMO level scores of young athletes ($t=1,362$, $p > 0.05$) do not differ significantly according to the club league status of the young athletes ($p=0.17$).

Table 6. T Test Results Regarding FOMO Levels of Youth Athletes According to Their Licence Status

Size	Licence	N	Average	Ss.	df	t	p
Fomo Variables	Amateur licence	176	26,69	7,59	198	1,38	0,16
	Professional Licence	24	24,33	9,56			

$p > 0.05$

When the findings in Table 6 are examined, the FOMO level scores of young athletes ($t=1,381$, $p > 0.05$) do not differ significantly according to the licence status of young athletes ($p=0,169$, $p > 0.05$).

Table 7. Anova Test Results Regarding FOMO Levels of Youth Athletes According to Age Variable

	N	Average	Ss.	f	p	Significant Difference
12-13 years old	45	25,26	6,70	4,15	0,00	16-17>18-19 16-17>20-21 16-17>12-13
14-15 years old	23	26,30	7,51			
16-17 years old	25	32,00	9,40			
18-19 years old	61	24,96	7,09			
20-21 years old	46	26,45	8,16			
Total	200	26,41	7,87			

$p < 0.05$

According to the results of the analysis in Table 7, a significant difference was observed between the age groups of the young athletes participating in the study between 16-17 years old, 18-19 years old and 20-21 years old, while no significant difference was observed between the other age groups ($p=0,00$). According to these results, the FOMO levels of young athletes aged 16-17 years are higher than those of young athletes aged 12-13 years, 18- 19 years and 20-21 years.

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Practice in Training Per Week

	N	Average	Ss.	f	p	Significant Difference
I attend all training sessions(1)	121	25,67	7,84	3,84	0,01	3>1 3>4
I attend at most one training session(2)	41	27,07	6,67			
I attend half of the training(3)	15	32,53	10,14			
I Attend Training Occasionally(4)	23	28,08	6,88			
Total	200	26,41	7,87			

p<0.05

According to the results of the analyses in Table 8, when the frequency of participation or frequency of training per week of the young athletes participating in the study was examined, a significant difference was found between I participate in half of the training and I participate in all training and I participate in training occasionally (p=0,01). According to these results, the FOMO levels of the young athletes who participated in half of the training sessions were higher than the young athletes who participated in all training sessions and who participated in training sessions occasionally.

Table 9. ANOVA Test Results Regarding FOMO Levels of Youth Athletes According to Years of Licenced Sport

	N	Average	Ss.	f	p
1-2 Years	79	26,74	7,42	0,912	0,43
3-4 Years	40	26,20	8,44		
5-6 Years	47	27,36	8,34		
7 Years and above	34	24,55	7,54		
Total	200	26,41	7,87		

p>0.05

According to the results of the analysis in Table 9, it was found that there was no significant difference in the FOMO levels of the young athletes participating in the study according to the years of licensed sports (p=0,43).

Discussion and Conclusion

In this study, FOMO (Fear of Missing Out) levels of young athletes were analysed in terms of different variables. The range of scores obtained from the FOMO scale varies between 10 and 50, and the higher the score of the individual, the more likely the individual is to have fear of missing developments. The findings show that young athletes have a moderate level of FOMO. This indicates that young athletes have the fear of following and missing the experiences of others with the effect of digital technology and social media use.

According to the results of the research, it is seen that FOMO levels of young athletes vary according to different variables. The first sub-problem of the research, gender variable was analysed. The findings reveal that FOMO levels of female athletes are significantly higher than male athletes. When the studies conducted are examined, there are studies that reveal that FOMO level differs according to gender variable. In the study of Przybylski et al. (2013), it was found that the FOMO levels of men were higher than those of women, while in the study conducted on adolescents, it was concluded that the FOMO levels of women were higher (Kartol & Peker, 2020). In addition, Przybylski et al. (2013) stated that as the age level increases, the FOMO levels of individuals do not change according to gender, but the FOMO levels of individuals aged 28 years and below tend to differentiate. In this context, since the average age of the participants in the current study is in the 18-19 age range, it can be said that the FOMO level differs according to gender.

In the second sub-problem of the study, it was examined whether the FOMO levels of young athletes differed according to individual and team sports. The findings show that the FOMO levels of young athletes participating in individual sports are higher than those participating in team sports. In the studies conducted, it is seen that the social skill levels of individuals engaged in individual sports are lower than individuals engaged in team sports (Gezer, Aslan, Dalkıran, & Kılıcıl, 2017).

realise themselves socially and feel excluded pushes them to spend more effort in order not to miss developments (Tanhan, Özok, & Tayiz, 2022). This may cause an increase in FOMO levels of individuals.

In the examination of FOMO levels of young athletes according to age groups, which is another sub- problem of the research, it was observed that the FOMO levels of 16-17 year old athletes were significantly higher compared to other age groups. However, no significant difference was found between 12-13, 18-19 and 20-21 age groups. This shows that FOMO levels in young athletes may vary depending on age groups. Przybylski et al. (2013) stated in their study that FOMO level differed according to age variable and FOMO level increased when the age level decreased to 28 years and below.

In another finding, FOMO levels of young athletes were examined according to the frequency of training participation or frequency of training per week. A significant difference was found between young athletes who participated in half of the training, young athletes who participated in all training and young athletes who participated in training occasionally. This shows that the frequency of participation of young athletes in training can affect their FOMO levels. Ceylan and Zekai (2021) found that individuals who do not participate in sportive activities have higher FOMO levels than individuals who participate in sportive activities.

It was determined that the FOMO levels of young athletes did not differ significantly according to their years of licensed sports, licence status and club league status.

As a result, it was found that FOMO levels of young athletes differed according to the variables of gender, age groups, individual or team sports and frequency of training participation, while FOMO levels did not differ significantly according to the variables of years of licensed sports, licence status and club league status.

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every sense, people are in the desire to follow and be involved in these changes and developments. Excessive excess of this desire reveals FOMO. Individuals with high FOMO level neglect other life requirements or do not show the necessary care. This feature may also be present in young athletes.

According to the results of the study, this feature is present in female, individual sportsmen and young athletes aged 16-17.

It may be important for coaches or educators working with young athletes to know the FOMO levels of their athletes and to take measures accordingly in terms of athletes' performances. In addition, it can be recommended to researchers to conduct studies examining the relationship between FOMO level and athletes' sportive performance

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